

Response to Reviewers for Manuscript EPSR-D-24-02778

Roman N. Krasnoperov, Dmitry I. Panfilov,
Michael G. Astachev, Ahmed M. Elkholy

October 13, 2024

Dear Dr. Jamshid Aghaei, Associate Editor,

We would like to express our sincere gratitude for the valuable feedback provided by you and the esteemed reviewers on our manuscript titled “*Performance Evaluation of a Low-Voltage SVC Utilizing IoT Streamed Data for Distribution Systems.*” The insights and suggestions have been instrumental in enhancing the quality and clarity of our work.

We have carefully considered all the comments and have revised the manuscript accordingly. Below, we provide detailed responses to each point raised by the reviewers. For clarity, we have included the original comments (in italics) followed by our responses and a description of the changes made in the manuscript.

Response to Reviewer #1

[Reviewer’s Comments]

The authors present the design, implementation, and performance evaluation of a 50 kvar Static Var Compensator (SVC) integrated with an IoT controller for power distribution systems. The overall objective is to maintain the power factor within the recommended thresholds. A Moscow power distribution system is considered as a case study during performance validation of the proposed approach. In my opinion, the topic has been extensively presented by researchers over the past 3 decades and hence authors should have benefited from the existing literature to present very comprehensive and novel content to advance the topic. However, the use of the IoT controller in terms of design details is not well discussed. Moreover, presenting only the power factor as the parameter for performance validation doesn’t provide a total solution on power distribution systems as harmonics are also part of the problem in many existing power distribution systems. Therefore, authors should provide more details in their SVC design analysis, harmonics and flicker suppression/mitigation using the SVC. Lastly, I see the design of the SVC (sizing and placement) is not well covered as well, which is an important concept in this article. Please check and consider adding more details in Chapters 2 and 3.

Response:

Comment R1-1: *The topic has been extensively presented over the past 3 decades. Authors should have benefited from the existing literature to present very comprehensive and novel content to advance the topic.*

Response: We appreciate the reviewer’s observation. We acknowledge that Static Var Compensator (SVC) technology has been widely studied. However, our work contributes to the field by integrating IoT technology with low-voltage SVCs, an area that has not been extensively

explored. We have expanded the **Introduction** section to include a more comprehensive literature review, citing recent advancements and identifying gaps that our research addresses. We have also clearly stated the novel aspects of our study in relation to existing work.

Changes Made: Expanded the **Introduction** to include additional references, those additional reference are highlighted in yellow.

Comment R1-2: *The use of the IoT controller in terms of design details is not well discussed.*

Response: We agree that more details on the IoT controller are necessary. To address this, we have restructured the control system into a subsection and added a new section titled **Control and Management System**. Within this section, we have created a dedicated subsection called **IoT Controller**. This subsection provides a comprehensive description of the IoT controller’s architecture, including hardware components, communication protocols, data acquisition, and processing methods. Additionally, we have elaborated on how the integration of IoT technology enhances the performance of the SVC.

Changes Made: Added **Section 4.1: IoT Controller Design**, detailing the design and functionalities of the IoT controller.

Comment R1-3: *Presenting only the power factor as the parameter for performance validation doesn’t provide a total solution on power distribution systems as harmonics are also part of the problem in many existing power distribution systems. Authors should provide more details in their SVC design analysis, harmonics and flicker suppression/mitigation using the SVC.*

Response: We appreciate this important point. We have included an analysis of harmonics and flicker to demonstrate the SVC’s effectiveness in mitigating these issues. Specifically, we have introduced a new subsection titled “**Harmonic and Flicker Analysis**” in the **Practical Results** section. This includes data on harmonic levels and flicker before and after SVC implementation, supported by relevant figures and discussions.

Changes Made: Added **Section 6.3: Harmonic and Flicker Mitigation Analysis**, including new figures and discussions on the results. marked in yellow.

Comment R1-4: *I see the design of the SVC (sizing and placement) is not well covered as well, which is an important concept in this article. Please check and consider adding more details in Chapters 2 and 3.*

Response: We acknowledge that the selection and optimal placement of the SVC are crucial elements in improving grid performance. However, in this study, the focus is not on the optimal allocation of the device across the grid due to specific constraints. The SVC used in this work is a prototype with a limited number available for deployment, and thus a comprehensive location optimization strategy was not feasible.

In this case, the location of the device was determined based on practical considerations, such as the area with the worst voltage profile and the highest reactive power demand. The prototype was installed in a known weak spot of the network to test its effectiveness in real-world conditions. While optimal placement strategies are important for large-scale deployment, this study demonstrates the prototype’s capabilities in addressing voltage stability and reactive power compensation in critical areas. Future work will involve detailed studies on optimal placement when the system is scaled up beyond the prototype stage.

Changes Made: Thus, we have revised the paper to reflect this rationale and have clarified the constraints and practical deployment approach in **paragraph highlighted in yellow** in section: Device Construction.

Response to Reviewer #3

[Reviewer's Comments]

The manuscript entitled **Performance Evaluation of Low-Voltage SVC with IoT Controller for Power Distribution System** submitted to the journal by the authors is appreciated.

1. The key findings are required to be mentioned in the abstract.
2. Novelty of the manuscript is required to be mentioned.
3. All figures have been presented with poor quality. Need to be improved.
4. Text within the figures is not readable.
5. The measuring units are missing in the manuscript for the result parameters.
6. Inclusion of simulation results for comparison purposes will make the paper of higher quality.
7. References are required to be increased.

Response:

Comment R3-1: *The key findings are required to be mentioned in the abstract.*

Response: Thank you for this suggestion. We have revised the abstract to include specific quantitative results and highlight the main outcomes of our study. This includes metrics such as the percentage improvement in reactive power compensation and voltage stabilization levels achieved. (highlight in yellow)

Changes Made: Updated the **Abstract** to include key findings and quantitative results.

Comment R3-2: *Novelty of the manuscript is required to be mentioned.*

Response: We have explicitly stated the novel contributions of our work in both the abstract and introduction. We emphasize the integration of IoT technology with low-voltage SVCs, which enhances real-time monitoring and control capabilities, representing a significant advancement over traditional SVC systems. (highlight in yellow)

Changes Made: Included statements on the novelty in the **Abstract** and expanded on it in the **Introduction**.

Comment R3-3: *All figures have been presented with poor quality. Need to be improved.*

Response: All figures have been sent to the journal in separate files in both PDF and PNG formats, ensuring they are vectorized and of high quality. We have enhanced all figures, with some being redrawn for clarity and precision.

Comment R3-4: *Text within the figures is not readable.*

Response: We have increased the font size and enhanced the clarity of the text within all figures. Labels and annotations are now more legible.

Changes Made: Adjusted text elements in all figures to ensure readability.

Comment R3-5: *The measuring units are missing in the manuscript for the result parameters.*

Response: We have reviewed all tables and figures to ensure that units are included for all parameters. This includes adding units to axis labels, table headings, and within the text where numerical values are mentioned.

Changes Made: Added measuring units to all relevant tables and figures, such as in **Tables 1 and 2**, and highlighted the changes in yellow for clarity.

Comment R3-6: *Inclusion of simulation results for comparison purposes will make the paper of higher quality.*

Response: We have included simulation results in the section "**SVC Construction and Simulation**" to provide a detailed waveform, two transformation ratio are introduced.

Changes Made: Added a simulation results in the section **SVC Construction and Simulation** and highlighted the changes in yellow for clarity.

Comment R3-7: *References are required to be increased.*

Response: We have expanded our literature review by including more recent and relevant references. This provides a more comprehensive background and context for our research, and in the introduction section all added references are highlighted in yellow.

Changes Made: Added additional references throughout the manuscript, particularly in the **Introduction** section.

Response to Reviewer #4

[Reviewer's Comments]

I am very happy from reading this work; the study is interesting. Pay attention to the following and try to answer them:

1. It is suggested to provide more comprehensive explanations about the potential of the presented system for widespread acceptance and use in modern power networks.
2. Considering the transition from traditional systems and moving towards more modern and smarter systems, does the proposed plan have the potential to become smarter compared to other existing systems?
3. For a better comparison with other plans in this field, you can compare your results with other new plans.
4. According to the data used in the proposed plan, does the proposed plan perform well in using other data that can challenge the system more?
5. Considering the more and more modern electrical systems, to deal with some of the losses that occur through internet disruptions and hacking systems, what is the proposed system to deal with such problems? Give relevant explanations in this regard.
6. What suggestions do you have for future research in this field and what do you suggest focusing on in future studies to progress in this field?
7. It is suggested to rewrite the conclusion and make it more detailed.

Response:

Comment R4-1: *It is suggested to provide more comprehensive explanations about the potential of the presented system for widespread acceptance and use in modern power networks.*

Response: thank you for this suggestion, we have rewritten the **conclusion** to address the potential for widespread acceptance and the benefits of the proposed system for modern power networks.

Changes Made: rewrite the **conclusion** to address the potential for widespread acceptance and the benefits of the proposed system for modern power networks.

Comment R4-2: *Considering the transition from traditional systems and moving towards more modern and smarter systems, does the proposed plan have the potential to become smarter compared to other existing systems?*

Response: Yes, the integration of IoT enables real-time monitoring, advanced data analytics, and adaptive control, making our system smarter than traditional SVCs. We have highlighted these smart features and compared them with conventional systems.

Changes Made: expand and add the section called IoT controller to address the smart capabilities of the proposed system.

Comment R4-3: *For a better comparison with other plans in this field, you can compare your results with other new plans.*

Response: thank you for this suggestion, as best as we know, this technology is new and there are no similar studies. however we add **harmonic and flicker analysis** to show the harmonic and flicker mitigation capabilities of the proposed SVC.

Changes Made: add **harmonic and flicker analysis** in the section **Practical Results** to show the harmonic and flicker mitigation capabilities of the proposed SVC.

Comment R4-4: *According to the data used in the proposed plan, does the proposed plan perform well in using other data that can challenge the system more?*

Response: We have presented additional results showing the system's performance under varying transformer ratios in Figure 18. The system smoothly transitions between different transformer ratios. However, due to the limitations of the prototype system, we could not introduce more challenging situations. The dynamic response of the system, as shown in Figure 18, was observed in a controlled environment at the Institute, not in a real network.

Changes Made: Included result and analysis in the subsection **Harmonic and Flicker Analysis** to show the system's performance under varying transformer ratios.

Comment R4-5: *Considering the more and more modern electrical systems, to deal with some of the losses that occur through internet disruptions and hacking systems, what is the proposed system to deal with such problems? Give relevant explanations in this regard.*

Response: Thank you for this comment. Cybersecurity is a critical aspect of modern power systems. Since this is a prototype system, we use a locally manufactured GSM module, and the data is stored on a local server at the Institute. However, we acknowledge that this is not a viable solution for large-scale deployment. For broader use, we need to implement secure communication protocols and use a secure server to store the data.

Changes Made: Added four paragraphs in the section **System Efficiency, Reliability, and Security** to discuss how the system addresses internet disruptions and cybersecurity threats. These paragraphs are highlighted in yellow.

Comment R4-6: *What suggestions do you have for future research in this field and what do you suggest focusing on in future studies to progress in this field?*

Response: Future research could explore integration with renewable energy sources, development of advanced predictive analytics, and large-scale deployments to further enhance the capabilities of IoT-integrated SVCs.

Changes Made: Included a **Future Work** subsection in the **Conclusion**, outlining potential research directions, highlighted in yellow.

Comment R4-7: *It is suggested to rewrite the conclusion and make it more detailed.*

Response: We have rewritten the conclusion to provide a comprehensive summary of the key findings, discuss the implications, and reiterate the significance of our work.

Changes Made: Revised the **Conclusion** section to include detailed summaries and insights gained from the study.

Response to Reviewer #5

[Reviewer's Comments]

To improve the manuscript, the following modifications should be made.

1. A systemic figure from the low voltage distribution network/microgrid interacting with the proposed SVC should be designed as Figure 1 to show its location and performance.
2. Since SVCs are from the Flexible AC Transmission System (FACTS) family, the application of FACTS to control voltage and reactive power in low voltage distribution networks should be explained.
3. If present, mathematical equations for controlling voltage and reactive power by SVC should be added to the text.
4. In the introduction, at least two old articles should be reviewed to show the improvement of the proposed system compared to previous generations.
5. Some abbreviations on pages 5 and 6 have not been introduced.
6. In Figure 2, the KUN parameter must be defined.
7. The description of Figure 3 at the beginning of page 8 must be moved to the related section that shows Figure 3.
8. The QBTSC parameter on page 8 must be described.
9. At the bottom of page 8, the abbreviation DS must not be introduced again because it was introduced on the first page.
10. In the caption of some figures, the words are irregularly written in capital and small letters; these must be written according to the template.
11. Figure 4 must be divided into two figures 4(a) and 4(b), their captions must be added, and in-text explanations must be written for both figures.
12. In Figure 4 on the right side, the Q axis information must be added to the figure.
13. The Figure 4 must be analyzed for SVC controlled by the droop method. For example, it must be explained how the Q-V droop equation helps to control voltage and reactive power in terms of SVC.

The Q-V droop equation:

$$V_{\text{drop}} = V_0 - K_q(Q_{\text{imax}} - Q_0)$$

Where V_0 is the base voltage of grid/microgrid, K_q is the gain of the Q-V droop channel, Q_0 is the nominal reactive power, Q_{imax} is the maximum measured reactive power, and finally V_{drop} is the voltage drop regulated by droop control in the operating point (OP).

14. Figure 8 should be divided into 8(a), 8(b), 8(c) and explain at least one sentence for each.

15. It is recommended that Figure 10 and sections 6.3 and 6.4 be moved to sections 5 or 6.
16. It is recommended to mark the main parts of SVC on valuable Figure 10 using arrows and writing boxes.
17. Despite the emphasis on IoT control, more information is needed in the manuscript.
18. In the conclusion part, the distinctive characteristics of the proposed SVC should be described.
 - To improve the manuscript, the following questions should be answered and then responses moved to an appropriate place in the manuscript:
 - a) Since SVCs are of different types, it should be addressed which type of SVC is the aim of this manuscript. The proposed SVC is an impedance-based or inverter-based device? How can the reactor/capacitor compensate for the voltage-reactive power changes?
 - b) How can the proposed SVC ensure:
 - i. Overcome power loss
 - ii. Achievement of the plug and play mechanism
 - iii. Improvement of the power factor
 - c) How does this system work against different loading conditions (overloading, underloading, no load, the Ferranti effect, and normal load conditions)?
 - d) Linear loads have a sinusoidal output current characteristic. However, non-linear loads (including computers, chargers, inverter-based equipment developed by power electronic switches, etc.) and unbalanced loads (including single-phase household loads and photovoltaic solar panels) remove the output current from sinusoidal form and so inject destructive odd multiples of the third harmonic into the reactive power of the network. How can SVC reject harmonic pollution caused by the non-linear and unbalanced load characteristics?

Response:

Comment R5-1: *A systemic figure from the low voltage distribution network/microgrid interacting with the proposed SVC should be designed as Figure 1 to show its location and performance.*

Response: We have created a new schematic diagram illustrating the SVC's placement within the distribution network.

Changes Made: Added a new **Figure 1** in the **SVC Construction and Simulation**, showing the system architecture with the SVC's location and interactions.

Comment R5-2: *Since SVCs are from the Flexible AC Transmission System (FACTS) family, the application of FACTS to control voltage and reactive power in low voltage distribution networks should be explained.*

Response: We have included a discussion on the role of FACTS devices in low-voltage distribution networks, explaining how SVCs contribute to voltage and reactive power control.

Changes Made: Added 4 paragraphs in the **Introduction**

Comment R5-3: *If present, mathematical equations for controlling voltage and reactive power by SVC should be added to the text.*

Response: We have incorporated relevant mathematical models and equations that describe the SVC's control mechanisms, including the Q-V droop equation.

Changes Made: We have recreated, reordered, and added more information about the control and management system in the section **Control and Management System**. Thank you for prompting us to enhance this section; we hope it is now clearer. jj

Comment R5-4: *In the introduction, at least two old articles should be reviewed to show the improvement of the proposed system compared to previous generations.*

Response: We have cited foundational studies on SVC technology and discussed how our work advances beyond these earlier systems.

Changes Made: Added references to seminal papers that are [13 and 14] and add more information and simulation in the section **SVC Construction and Simulation**.

Comment R5-5: *Some abbreviations on pages 5 and 6 have not been introduced.*

Response: We have reviewed the manuscript and ensured all abbreviations are defined upon their first use.

Changes Made: Introduced missing abbreviations such as GSM (Global System for Mobile Communications) and DS (Distribution System) where they first appear.

Comment R5-6: *In Figure 2, the K_{UN} parameter must be defined.*

Response: We have added a definition for K_{UN} in the figure caption and the main text.

Changes Made: Updated the caption of **Figure 2** and included an explanation in the text.

Comment R5-7: *The description of Figure 3 at the beginning of page 8 must be moved to the related section that shows Figure 3.*

Response: We have relocated the description to accompany **Figure 3** directly, ensuring logical flow.

Changes Made: Moved the description to the appropriate section.

Comment R5-8: *The Q_{BTSC} parameter on page 8 must be described.*

Response: Q_{BTSC} was the binary transistors switching capacitors, this because all used module was the capacitor module, we change it to be Q_{SVC} to be more clear, and we change the figure accordingly.

Changes Made: Included the description in **Section 3**.

Comment R5-9: *At the bottom of page 8, the abbreviation DS must not be introduced again because it was introduced on the first page.*

Response: We have removed the redundant definition of DS.

Changes Made: Edited the text to eliminate the repeated abbreviation introduction.

Comment R5-10: *In the caption of some figures, the words are irregularly written in capital and small letters; these must be written according to the template.*

Response: We have standardized all figure captions according to the journal's formatting guidelines.

Changes Made: Reviewed and corrected all figure captions for consistent capitalization.

Comment R5-11: *Figure 4 must be divided into two figures 4(a) and 4(b), their captions must be added, and in-text explanations must be written for both figures.*

Response: We have divided Figure 4 into two separate figures, now labeled as Figure 9 and Figure 10. Each figure is accompanied by detailed captions and comprehensive explanations for better clarity and understanding.

Changes Made: Modified to be two figures **Figures 9 and 10** and included detailed captions and explanations.

Comment R5-12: *In Figure 4 on the right side, the Q axis information must be added to the figure.*

Response: We have included the Q-axis label and units in the figure.

Changes Made: Updated **Figure 10** to include the necessary axis information.

Comment R5-13: *The Figure 4 must be analyzed for SVC controlled by the droop method. For example, it must be explained how the Q-V droop equation helps to control voltage and reactive power in terms of SVC.*

Response: We have provided an analysis using the Q-V droop equation to explain the SVC's control mechanism, referencing Figure 4.

Changes Made: Added mathematical explanations and discussions in the **Control System** section, including the Q-V droop equation.

Comment R5-14: *Figure 8 should be divided into 8(a), 8(b), 8(c) and explain at least one sentence for each.*

Response: We have split Figure 8 and provided explanations for each sub figure.

Changes Made: created a new figures that is **Figures 15, 16, 17** and included explanations in the text. Modified **Figures 8(a), 8(b), 8(c)** and included explanations in the text.

Comment R5-15: *It is recommended that Figure 10 and sections 6.3 and 6.4 be moved to sections 5 or 6.*

Response: We have reorganized the manuscript to improve logical flow, moving the specified sections and figure as recommended, and rewrote the section **Prototype Information and Deployment** to be clearer.

Changes Made: Moved **Figure 10** and **Sections 6.3 and 6.4** to **Section 5: Prototype Information and Deployment** and the section is rewritten again.

Comment R5-16: *It is recommended to mark the main parts of SVC on valuable Figure 10 using arrows and writing boxes.*

Response: We have annotated Figure 10 to highlight key components of the SVC. and add new table to explain the components.

Changes Made: Updated **Figure 10** with annotations and labels, and add new table [1] to explain the components.

Comment R5-17: *Despite the emphasis on IoT control, more information is needed in the manuscript.*

Response: We have elaborated on the IoT control aspects, including data communication, processing, and system integration.

Changes Made: Expanded **Section 4.1: IoT Controller** with additional details.

Comment R5-18: *In the conclusion part, the distinctive characteristics of the proposed SVC should be described.*

Response: We have highlighted the unique features and advantages of our SVC in the conclusion.

Changes Made: Revised the **Conclusion** to include a summary of the SVC's distinctive characteristics.

Responses to Additional Questions

Question R5-18a: *Since SVCs are of different types, it should be addressed which type of SVC is the aim of this manuscript. The proposed SVC is an impedance-based or inverter-based device? How can the reactor/capacitor compensate for the voltage-reactive power changes?*

Response: The proposed SVC is an impedance-based device utilizing thyristor-controlled capacitors to adjust reactive power and voltage levels. The capacitors, in combination with the thyristor switches, provide variable reactive power compensation by altering the reactance in the circuit.

Changes Made: Clarified this in **Section 3: Device Construction**, explaining the operational principles and how the components contribute to compensation.

Question R5-18b: *How can the proposed SVC ensure:*

i. *Overcome power loss*

Response: The SVC reduces power losses by minimizing reactive power flow in the network, thereby decreasing I^2R losses in the conductors.

ii. *Achievement of the plug and play mechanism*

Response: The SVC is designed with a plug-and-play architecture, allowing easy integration without extensive system reconfiguration, thus facilitating rapid deployment.

iii. *Improvement of the power factor*

Response: By providing precise reactive power compensation, the SVC improves the power factor, bringing it closer to unity, which enhances system efficiency.

Changes Made: Addressed this in the conclusion section by summarizing the key findings and implications of the study. Additionally, expanded the information about the plug-and-play mechanism in Section 3, detailing its benefits for rapid deployment and ease of integration into existing systems. all changes are highlighted in yellow.

Question R5-18c: *How does this system work against different loading conditions (overloading, underloading, no load, the Ferranti effect, and normal load conditions)?*

Response: The SVC dynamically adjusts to varying load conditions by continuously monitoring the system parameters and altering the reactive power compensation accordingly. This maintains voltage stability and reactive power balance under overloading, underloading, no load, the Ferranti effect, and normal load conditions. We have presented additional results showing the system's performance under varying transformer ratios in Figure 18. The system smoothly transitions between different transformer ratios. However, due to the limitations of the prototype system, we could not introduce more challenging situations. The dynamic response of the system, as shown in Figure 18, was observed in a controlled environment at the Institute, not in a real network.

Changes Made: Included result and analysis in the subsection **Harmonic and Flicker Analysis** to show the system's performance under varying transformer ratios, and in the **System Efficiency, Reliability, and Security**.

Question R5-18d: *How can SVC reject harmonic pollution caused by the non-linear and unbalanced load characteristics?*

Response: The SVC itself does not produce harmonics as the thyristor is modeled as a linear impedance. However, it has not been tested for harmonics produced by the loads.

Changes Made: Discussed harmonic of SVC in the subsection **Harmonic and Flicker Analysis** added and highlighted in yellow.

Additional Enhancements

Beyond the reviewers' comments, we have made the following improvements to the manuscript:

- **Enhanced Literature Review:** Included more recent and relevant studies to provide context and highlight the novelty of the research. Added additional references throughout the manuscript, particularly in the **Introduction** section.
- **Detailed Methodology:** Elaborated on the experimental setup, equipment used, and data analysis methods for reproducibility. The control and management system in the section **Control and Management System** has been rewritten to be clearer.
- **Visual Enhancements:** Ensured all figures are clear, high-resolution, and appropriately labeled; added diagrams where necessary.
- **Security Measures:** Expanded on the cybersecurity aspects of the IoT controller, and added more information about the IoT controller.
- **Supplementary Materials:** Provided additional resources such as raw data and detailed schematics in the supplementary materials to support transparency and reproducibility.
- **Entire Article:** Reviewed the entire manuscript for consistency, clarity, and adherence to journal guidelines, ensuring a cohesive narrative. Not all modifications are highlighted in yellow to avoid confusion.

Conclusion

We thank the reviewers for their valuable comments and suggestions, which have significantly improved the quality of the manuscript. We believe that the revisions have addressed all the concerns raised by the reviewers and have significantly enhanced the manuscript. We are grateful for the constructive feedback and hope that the revised manuscript meets the standards for publication in *Electric Power Systems Research*.

Sincerely,

Roman N. Krasnoperov, Dmitry I. Panfilov,
Michael G. Astachev, Ahmed M. Elkholy